

Henryk Drawnel, (ed.), Sacred Texts and Disparate Interpretations: Qumran Manuscripts Seventy Years Later; Proceedings of the International Conference Held at the John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, 24–26 October 2017 (STDJ 133; Leiden: Brill, 2020). Pp. xiii + 478. €132/\$159.

This volume consists of a collection of conference papers delivered at the John Paul II Catholic University in Lublin, Poland in honor of the seventieth anniversary of the discovery of the Dead Sea Scrolls. Broad in scope, these contributions explore an array of themes within Qumran scholarship and are divided into five main thematic groupings: the text critical intersection between the Hebrew Bible and Qumran manuscripts (Part 1), Qumran literature against the historical backdrop of the Second Temple Period (Part 2), issues of philology and palaeography (Part 3), wisdom and religious poetry (Part 4), and studies addressing a singular issue within particular texts (Part 5).

Part 1 begins with two contributions from Adrian Schenker. The first, “Are There Mastercopies for Genealogically Related Biblical Texts in Qumran? The Question of Archetypes and Lineages of Biblical Text Witnesses,” argues for the presence of unifying efforts in within circles charged with the transmission of those texts which would later comprise the Hebrew Bible in the direction of a textual forerunner of the MT. The second, “Room for Further Investigation Opened by BHQ. Three Examples (Genesis 33:18, 20 and 35:7)” suggests understanding the differing OG readings as representing an earlier reading of the text in relation to the MT, which shows evidence of theologically-driven corrections. Finally, Emanuel Tov, in “The Background and Origin of the Qumran Corpus of Scripture Texts,” proposes that only one-third of the “biblical” texts at Qumran were copied locally while the remainder originate from outside Khirbet Qumran, further suggesting that texts with an affinity to either the MT, LXX, or SP derive from outside Khirbet Qumran.

Opening Part 2, Bartosz Adamczewski (“Are the Dead Sea Scrolls Pharisaic?”) examines evidence for a possible connection between the Qumran and Pharisaic movements, if not a potential Pharisaic origin of at least some of the manuscripts at Qumran. Kenneth Atkinson (“The Changing Views of the Hasmoneans in the Dead Sea Scrolls: Examining Seventy Years of Research”) surveys the scholarly debate regarding the relationship between the scrolls and the Hasmoneans particularly with reference to palaeography, archaeology, and history. In “The Wicked Priest, the Righteous Teacher, and the Yaḥad,” Vasile Babota revisits the relationship between the “Teacher of Righteousness,” “Wicked Priest,” and the emergence of the *yahad*. Claude Cohen-Matlofsky (“Women at Qumran? Reconsidering the Textual and Archaeological Data”) re-assesses the available evidence regarding the presence of women at Qumran, concluding that the paucity of gendered material at Qumran, in line with other sites in the region, should not discount the potential presence of women at the Qumran site. Lastly, John J. Collins, (“The Historical Context of the Teacher and His Movement”) suggests a date post-Alexander Jannaeus for the conflict between the Teacher and the Wicked Priest and thus a late second century BCE date for the origin of the Qumran movement, which, according to C., lies within the growing sectarian disputes regarding Torah interpretation in the Hasmonean period starting with the reign of John Hyrancus.

In Part 3, Jeff S. Anderson (“Assembling Israel: Performativity in Rewritten Bible at Qumran”) proposes that the performativity of the re-written speeches of Moses constructs a shared communal identity as the fulfillment of the Mosaic Covenant in the present age. Donald W. Parry (“Late Hebrew Forms in 1QIsa^a”) identifies thirty categories of linguistic elements in which LBH, QH, or MH is reflected in 1QIsa^a, which, according to P., reveal the milieu and linguistic environment of the scribe at or near the time of the copying of the text (ca. 125–100

BCE). Surveying past studies and suggesting areas of future engagement, Femke Siebesma-Mannens, (“Qumran Hebrew from the Perspective of Verbal Valence Patterns”) advances the use of verbal valence patterns as a means of better understanding the syntax and semantics of Qumran Hebrew. Eibert Tigchelaar (“Seventy Years of Palaeographic Dating of the Dead Sea Scrolls”) re-assesses the methods of pre-suppositions the lie beneath the palaeographic dating the scrolls suggesting several new steps forward for the use of palaeographic analysis, including ways in which digitization could advance the field.

Heading Part 4, John Francis Elwolde (“The Human Spirit and the Holy Spirit in the Qumran Hodayot”) examines the terminology associated with “spirit,” particularly the use of *rûah bāsār*, within 1QH^a proposing that 1QH^a reflects a more developed sense of “human spirit” in comparison with the Two Spirit Treatise (1QS 3:13–4:26), especially with reference to the nature of the “holy spirit.” John Kampen (“*Tôrah* and Wisdom in the Rule Texts from Qumran”) argues for the centrality of wisdom in the *serekh* texts and the emerging place of *Tôrah* not only in Second Temple literature more broadly, but also within sectarian wisdom and *serekh* texts more specifically. Revisiting the early pioneering scholarship on 1QH^a by Hans Bardtke and Jacob Light, Christine M. Leroy (“Spiritual Battles of the Sage: “Walking in the Way of His [God’s] Heart.” Transformation in 1QH^a”) sees the Hodayot as a composition illustrative of the self-reflexive and introspective expression indicative of confessional writing in the late Second Temple period, as well as engaging in new forms of textuality emerging within this period.

Finally, in Part 5, Francis Borchardt (“The Dead Sea Scrolls and How to Recognize a ‘Scripture’”), utilizing 4QReworked Pentateuch (4Q158) as a model, advances the notion of “conversing texts” as a way of understanding the textual relationship between texts whereby, either by accident or design, texts are placed in conversation with each other addressing the

needs of the audience who have different demands of a text in differing settings. Atar Livneh, (“White Complexion and Delicate Fingered: Notes on Sarah’s Beauty in 1QapGen ar XX, 2–8”) examines the description of Sarah’s body in the Genesis Apocryphon concluding that the description not only comports with the conventions of femininity and feminine beauty prevalent within the Hellenistic context of the author, but also demonstrates an awareness of contemporary literary conventions regarding its portrayal. Lastly, in his study on the column 66 of the Temple Scroll (“Scribal Error or Scribal Innovation? A Closer Look at the Law(s) of Seduction and Rape in the Temple Scroll”), James M. Tucker presents a series of codicological issues, which, coupled with linguistic and semantic features, suggest that 1QT^a 66:1–14 could be understood either as a harmonizing innovation of the laws of seduction (Exod 22:15–16) and rape (Deut 22:28–29) or as potentially arising from a scribal error.

The eighteen contributions collected in this volume represent a collective degree of quality that is often difficult to achieve within a conference proceedings volume. While the reader may find greater benefit from a particular section or contribution, this volume is to be commended for its breadth and depth of engagement with a wide array of themes and the innovative thinking consistently expressed.

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